

Zybertspheres - GPS Correction

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2025-09-01

In Zybert Cosmology the universe comprises Zybertspheres, (Z). Ours has an antineutron core, enveloped by a matter-antimatter creation zone, enveloped by a growing expanding spherical neutron cloud. Core gravity, (a), is all pervasive affecting all matter and antimatter and light. (a) acts radially from (Z) centres along the Axis of Zybert which increases GPS EMR c-hat.

In Zybert Cosmology light has 3 speeds, c - Eigen, c-hat - Relative and (C) - Absolute or (Z) speed. c is speed relative to emitters, c-hat is speed relative to receivers and (C) is speed relative to (Z) centres fixed in fixed space. c is additive with emitter, receiver and reflector speed, and gravity.

In Zybert Cosmology Doppler shift is expressed as

$$\hat{f} / f = \hat{c} / c \quad \hat{c} = c - v \quad v \text{ is emitter-receiver relative velocity}$$

also, $\Delta \hat{f} / f = \Delta \hat{c} / c$

GPS satellites orbit earth at 3,844.544m/s and 20,197,267.2m altitude using L-band 10.23Mhz. In Zybert Cosmology light speed is additive with acceleration by gravity and velocity of emitter, thus GPS satellite EMR c-hat > c from earth's gravity and c-hat < c from velocity of prograde GPS orbits and both are compensated by GPS satellite clock frequency corrections.

The spreadsheet simulation [1] allows velocity and altitude to be varied, 0% to 200%, to show corresponding frequency corrections. It uses 2,000 steps, and for comparison, code in [1] used 32-digit precision and dt = 1e-7s, showing a small but significant difference

$$\Delta \hat{c}.g = 0.158832 \quad f = 10.229999995421300\text{Mhz (spreadsheet)}$$

$$\Delta \hat{c}.g = 0.158681 \quad f = 10.229999995426400\text{Mhz.}$$

Code in [1] shows (C)v has no current practical effect on frequency correction,

$$\Delta c.g = 0.15868147 \quad f = 10.229999995426405\text{Mhz} \quad (C) = (C)c + (C)v * \text{Cos}(90)$$

$$\Delta c.g = 0.15868275 \quad f = 10.229999995426361\text{Mhz} \quad (C) = (C)c + (C)v * \text{Cos}(0)$$

(Z)A also has an effect but is also small, because of the small distance.

The following table from [1], has Δc-hat.g (increase in light speed by earth gravity) calculated using the code given in [1] with 32-digit precision and dt = 1e-7s.

Δc-hat.g m/s	0.158681475924497	by earth's gravity
c-hat.R m/s	299,792,458.134030000000000	sqrt((c+Δc-hat.g)^2 - v^2)
Δc-hat = c-hat.R - c m/s	0.134030000000000	
c-hat m/s	299,792,457.865970000000000	c - Δc-hat (corrected speed)
z	0.99999999952923	c-hat / c
(Z) corrected GPS clock Mhz	10.229999995426400	z * 10.23Mhz
corrected GPS clock Mhz	10.229999995430000	
GPS clock L-band Mhz	10.230000000000000	

Note: the spreadsheet calculation for Δc-hat displayed 0.134030222892761 and has been corrected.

[1] Zybertspheres - Phenomena.xlsx see <https://zenodo.org/records/17034092>